

2025

The Phonoautobothy Report

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The Phonoautobothy

2024 evaluation

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Science Ceilidh

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#phonoautobothy #deargreenmusicscene

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Summary

The Phonoautobothly is a unique solar-powered multi-purpose music trailer. This creative project, led by the University of Glasgow, brings together art and engineering science to showcase the use of renewable energy for power generation on a small scale to diverse communities in Glasgow.

Through encouraging families and adults alike to get hands on with instruments and record music powered only through solar energy, along with wider engineering activities highlighting other renewable energy including racing wind-powered cars, the Phonoautobothly aimed to prompt interest and inspire a deeper understanding of renewable energy locally, including new awareness of alternative means of energy generation different to diesel. Through this, the mobile music trailer looked to promote a positive attitude towards the practical steps that can be taken towards the environmental transition in Glasgow and understanding of the role of research to achieve this. The mobile nature of the activities meant it could be embedded in community settings and arts festivals, enabling the activities to connect with audiences who both have not previously engaged with university research and who are also newer to renewable energy conversations. For those involved in delivering the activities, like the volunteer researchers, the project aimed to foster new skills and confidence in public engagement and build new collaborations across disciplines and organisations including Glasgow Life and Beatroute Arts.

The first phase of the project involved delivering six Phonoautobothly engagement events collaborating with community partners and music festivals across the city of Glasgow. The project's activities were tailored to each event, but generally participants got involved in two main components of the Phonoautobothly. The first was a one-of-a-kind solar-powered trailer where participants were offered a free 20-minute slot to play, record a sample of music of their choice and transfer the result to a cassette tape which could then be decorated and taken home. The side panels were often opened so passers-by could watch and there were also performances from the booth. Drawn in through the format, the intention was to engage on the role of engineering in music production, including the energy and science that powered the Phonoautobothly - even in a cloudy Glasgow! An engineering stall complemented the off-grid studio, focusing on connecting attendees with researchers and creating an accessible and engaging space for families with short "hook" activities, including colouring, engineering games and building a wind-powered car. Here whole families could talk with engineers and volunteers, who facilitated informal conversations, and ask questions on renewable energy topics as they built together, including portable renewable power, transition from diesel to low carbon power, community energy in the city, and different renewable energy sources.

Part 1: Underpinning Research

Graeme Hunt has developed a research interest in the engineering that makes cultural production possible, while Hunt and Gioia Falcone are running Glasgow postcode analysis of clean energy transition challenges via GALLANT, which can be complemented by qualitative engagement in those same communities via this project.¹

Matt Brennan's research into the music industries and environmental sustainability underpins the Phonoautobothly as an artistic disruption, which complements – and add a new dimension to – Hunt's work and Glasgow's UKRI-funded GALLANT project.²

Brennan and data scientist Mark Wong have analyzed fan attitudes towards climate actions in the music sector and developed social network analysis methods to examine the organizational relationships between Glasgow's cultural organizations, energy suppliers, transport, and other carbon-intensive infrastructures.³

Meanwhile, Inge Sorenson's research into the screen sector and sustainability, along with her RSE-funded collaboration with Wong, have identified areas of infrastructural overlap between the music and screen industries from an environmental sustainability perspective.⁴ Both Sorenson and Wong collaborated with Brennan and Hunt in the later stage of this project, providing a foundation for future work to apply our findings beyond the music sector to screen and other cultural industries.

The Phonoautobothly project itself was designed to deliberately blur the lines between public engagement, impact, and research. We engaged a range of audiences and stakeholders while researching their attitudes throughout the project, with a view to creating impact and accelerating just and green transition. We also gained understanding of how the definition of 'research' changes across disciplinary and institutional contexts within and beyond the university.

¹ Hunt, G. 2023. Introduction to Portable Renewable Energy Technologies. European Broadcasting Union Roundtable: Energy on Sets. <https://tech.ebu.ch/events/2023/roundtable-energy-on-sets>. See also Falcone and Hunt's forthcoming work on a post-code community energy needs analysis work package for the GALLANT (Glasgow as a Living Lab Accelerating Novel Transformation) research project. These same communities will be engaged via cultural interventions, offering a significant interdisciplinary perspective. GALLANT is supported by the Natural Environment Research Council as part of the Changing the Environment Programme. NERC grant reference number – NE/W005042/1.

² Brennan, M. (2020) The environmental sustainability of the music industries. In: Oakley, K. and Banks, M. (eds.) Cultural Industries and the Environmental Crisis: New Approaches for Policy. Springer International Publishing, pp. 37-49. ISBN 9783030493837 (doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-49384-4_4). See also Brennan, M. (2021) The infrastructure and environmental consequences of live music. In: Devine, K. and Boudreault-Fournier, A. (eds.) Audible Infrastructures: Music, Sound, Media. Oxford University Press: Oxford, pp. 117-134. ISBN 9780190932633 (doi: 10.1093/oso/9780190932633).

³ Shaw, D., Brennan, M., McKeever, D. and Wong, M. (2022) 'Turn Up the Volume' Survey: Music Fan Attitudes towards Climate Change and Music Sustainability. Glasgow: University of Glasgow.

⁴ Sørensen, I. E. and Noonan, C. (2022) Production, policy and power: the screen industry's response to the environmental crisis. *Media, Culture and Society*, 44(1), pp. 172-184. (doi: 10.1177/01634437211065697)

Part 2: Methodology

How did we gather data?

The evaluation was adapted to capture the expected impacts of the project using a mix of qualitative and quantitative data.

A range of methods were used to track attendees' numbers and measure behavioural change in participants' understanding of renewable energy after the events. A postcard activity was developed and embedded in the Phonoautobothly activities during the events to monitor attendees' numbers, backgrounds and feedback, and their perspectives on sustainability. Similarly, posters with prompts ('graffiti wall') and stickers were used to gauge engagement with the activities and attitudes of community members around the use of renewable energy. A separate online survey was used to gather qualitative feedback from participants that engaged with the project at the Belle & Sebastian festival. A Lego activity was used at the Beatroute Arts event as a complement to the postcards to gather participants' views on the project and on the use of renewable energy for it.

These methods shed light on the impact the project had on audiences, and especially allowed for evaluation of new awareness of university research in sustainability, and access to research from groups who have not engaged with the university before. Creative tools, conversations with attendees, and observations were used across the events to collect data about participants' interest in taking practical steps towards environmental sustainability in Glasgow and their understanding of alternative sources of energy.

After the events, debrief meetings with the volunteers and organisers were conducted to gather information about the impact of the project on core collaborators. These interviews, along with a survey, were used to draw ideas about the volunteer experience and the Phonoautobothly as a public engagement project. We also conducted a post-hoc analysis of the carbon dioxide emissions from the events (methodology for this is detailed in Part 5 of this report).

What happened at the events?

The Phonoautobothy appeared at six events throughout the summer and autumn of 2024 in Glasgow, showcasing sustainable energy in action for producing live and recording music.

The first three events were held as part of the wider [WestFest Festival](#).

The first took place on the 9th of June at **The Kelvingrove Bandstand**. The festival was busy, with an estimated capacity of 600 people in total, of which half engaged with the project by actively discussing with researchers and watching the mobile solar-powered studio performances. The event was friendly, attracting a diverse audience including mostly families with young children.

The second event was held at the **Advanced Research Centre, University of Glasgow** (ARC) on the 15th of June, and also attracted a diverse audience of

professionals, non-professionals, and families. The main event had a broad capacity of 850 people, the largest public event ever held at the ARC, of which approximately half engaged with the project by actively discussing with researchers and volunteers at some point. This was a sustainably powered event with 2 stages, one powered by hydrogen and one powered by solar energy.

The third was held at **Mansfield Park** on the 22nd of June. This was a smaller event with around 150 attendees who were primarily families. The majority engaged with the project by actively engaging with researchers through the activities. In all these events, the solar-powered music recording and live production studio offered slots to record a cassette tape and a space and materials to decorate it.

Following that, the Phonoautobothy appeared at the **Belle & Sebastian music festival** on the 2nd and 3rd of August. Although the main event was held at the SWG3 section of the festival with a capacity of 2,500 people, around 125 participants engaged

with the project activities recording music in the solar-powered studio (this was fully booked out) and watching the performances, with fewer getting involved in the engineering activities. This was an afternoon and evening event, attracting a primarily adult audience with many international attendees. The activities were quieter but treated as a big feature in the wider festival, as this mobile studio was designed to power live music events and produce high quality recordings without relying on the usual diesel generators. At this music festival, eight professional artists (Alison Eales of Butcher Boy, Chris Geddes of Belle & Sebastian, Carla J Easton of the Vaselines, and 5-piece band CMAT) got involved and recorded in the solar-powered studio.

In early autumn, the music trailer travelled to **Castlemilk** to take part in the University of Glasgow **Explorathon Community Day**. Held on the 27th of September, the event was organised completely in a community setting (Glasgow Club Castlemilk) with an

audience of mostly families. The music trailer was set up outside the building with its wings extended, offering a stage where lots of people stood to watch the recordings and with children joining in to decorate the cassette tapes. The event had a broad capacity of 280 people, of which around 60% engaged with the project by chatting with researchers in the engineering stall and recording music in the Phonoautobothy.

The final event of this phase of the programme was held on the 1st of October with partner community-led charity **Beatroute Arts**. This particular session took place in the Northeast of Glasgow at the Beatroute Arts Centre, engaging the regular attendees of

their adult programme, including older people and adults with disabilities that come together to take part in creative activities. The delivery format was co-produced together, with music tutors along with the researchers facilitating one-to-one recording sessions with the participants in the music trailer, located outside the building. The engineering tables were found separately inside the building, where participants and their companions engaged in short activities, chatted about energy sources and drew their own sustainable inventions.

Beatroute participants used a sensory approach and built a car with a wind turbine (top) and a wind-powered tower (below) with Lego.

Part 3: Who did we reach?

An estimated 1710 people engaged with the Phonoautobothy Activities across six events in some way including watching performances, with around 67.3% (1150) of individuals having had a direct conversation with the researchers involved.

Based on a smaller subset of people (140, 8.2% of those in conversation) who were monitored using a postcard activity, the Phonoautobothy reached participants who generally haven't had contact with researchers from the University of Glasgow before - two thirds had never or rarely been in contact with them before.

Around half of those who engaged were interested and already engaging in renewable energy, though a significant proportion (one third) are "open but don't go out of their way to engage" in the topic.

Event and Date	Characteristics	Audience summary	Activities and participants engaged	Data from postcards
WestFest – 9 Jun	Open local event held in a community setting (Kelvingrove Bandstand, G12 8NR)	Venue general capacity of 600 people. Audience with a strong family focus, mostly young children under 10 and middle-aged adults.	300 people engaged broadly with the project, with all persons having had a direct conversation with the researchers and volunteers involved. The trailer was used as a stage and for participants to record their own tape.	30 people were monitored using postcards (10% of the participants that actively engaged with the activities).
WestFest - 15 Jun	Open local event held at the Advanced Research Centre (ARC, University of Glasgow, G11 6EW)	Venue general capacity of 850 people. Predominantly adult audience between 30 and 64.	Almost all people engaged broadly (e.g. watching performances) and 400 actively engaged with the project by having conversations with volunteers and taking part in the activities. The trailer was used as a stage and for participants to record their own tape. The event was sustainably powered with 2 stages (one was powered by a hydrogen reactor and one powered by solar energy).	45 people were monitored using postcards (11.3% of the participants that actively engaged with the activities).
WestFest - 22 Jun	Open local event held in a community location (Mansfield Park, G11 5QP)	Venue general capacity of 150 people. Audience with a strong family focus, mostly young children under 10 and middle-aged adults.	Approximately 125 people engaged broadly with the project, with all persons, having conversations with volunteers and taking part in the activities. The trailer was used as a stage and for participants to record their own tape.	14 people were monitored using postcards (11.2% of the participants that actively engaged with the activities).
Belle & Sebastian - 2&3 Aug	Event held at a ticketed commercial music festival (SWG3 arts venue, on the banks of the River Clyde, G3 8QG)	General capacity of 2,500 persons across two days. Predominantly adult audience with many international attendees.	125 people engaged with the project broadly, with all persons having had a direct conversation with the researchers and volunteers involved. The trailer was used as a stage for professional artists and for participants to record their own tape.	13 people were monitored using postcards (10.4 of the participants engaged). An additional online survey was applied to a subset of people that engaged with the project at the festival (18 responses: 17 attendees and 1 performer).
Explorathon - 27 Sept	Open local event held in a community location (Glasgow Club Castlemilk, G45 9NH).	Venue general capacity of 283 people. The audience were predominantly young children between 5 and 10 and middle-aged adults.	Almost all people engaged broadly (e.g. watching performances) and 175 had direct conversations with volunteers and researchers while taking part in the activities. The trailer was used for participants to record their own tape.	35 people were monitored using postcards (20% of the participants that actively engaged with the activities).
Beatroute Arts - 1 Oct	Event held in partnership with the community-led charity Beatroute Arts in their centre (Balornock, North East of Glasgow, G21 3RP) exclusively for the participants of their adult programme.	Venue general capacity of 30 people. The participants were regular attendees of Beatroute adult programme and their companions, including older people and adults with disabilities, and Beatroute staff as well.	Almost all attendees engaged broadly (e.g. watching the final performance) and 25 had direct conversations with volunteers and researchers while taking part in the activities. The trailer was used for participants to record their own tape in one-one slots.	3 persons were monitored using postcards (12% of the participants that actively engaged with the activities).
Total overall	6 events	General participants/capacity across all events: 4,413	Participants engaged broadly (e.g. watch performances): 1,710 Participants actively engaged by having direct conversations or taking part in the activities with the researchers and volunteers: 1,150	140 people represented in the postcards filled (12.2% of the participants monitored).

Age of attendees

Based on observations and interview data from the volunteer facilitators, the Phonoautoboth activities primarily engaged young people and families. Our evaluation methodology mainly comprised activity postcards filled out by adults.

Based on the monitoring postcards, the groups with the greatest engagement were young people under 18, comprising one third of respondents, and middle-aged adults between 31 - 45 years, also comprising one third. The remaining groups were the 18-30-year-olds at 11.4%, and over 45s at 20%. The Beatroute Arts event was adult only, the Belle & Sebastian festival had a predominantly adult audience, and the rest were family orientated. With around 34% of the respondents of the postcards being under 18 (and 30% under 10 years), there is still likely an older bias in terms of who filled out the postcards, and younger ages who did engage in most events are still likely underrepresented in this data (though at times parents filled out postcards on their behalf).

Age of attendees

Prior contact with University of Glasgow researchers

Based on this sample, the Phonoautoboth engaged participants who hadn't had contact with University of Glasgow (UoG) Researchers before. A majority of respondents indicated that they have never (37.1%) or rarely (27.9%) had contact with UoG

researchers before the event. This might imply that the survey reached a broader audience beyond those already engaged with the university. While some respondents had some contact, the frequencies are relatively low, with "sometimes" (22.1%) being the most common category after "rarely".

The University of Glasgow general public audience feedback survey provides a glimpse into the public engagement in UoG events across subjects and research fields, including film screenings, music events, exhibitions, family days, talks, workshops, and performances. Data from 415 responses to this survey, taken from between 2022 and 2024, shows 30% of audience members had not been to a UoG event before.

The results of the Phonoautobothly monitoring postcards are likely a conservative estimate as the majority of people engaged didn't complete a postcard. However, even based on these statistics and comparing them to previous similar statistics above, gathered at University of Glasgow campus-based events, the Phonoautobothly did seem to reach more new audiences comparatively.

Frequency of contact of participants with UoG researchers before the event

Interest around renewable energy and sustainability

When participants were asked what their interest level with regards to renewable energy was, around half of those who engaged specifically in the postcards indicated they were already interested in conversations around renewable energy. Almost two thirds of respondents had a strong interest in renewable energy - selecting either "interested & actively engaging in the topic" (50.7%) or "work or study in the topic" (10%). This suggests a motivated and engaged audience for research and outreach initiatives in this

field. However, a significant proportion were open to it but didn't go out of their way to engage in renewable energy (35.7%). This still indicates a potential audience for raising awareness and promoting further engagement with renewable energy topics. Very few weren't interested in the topic (less than 1%), suggesting that in general the participants did already have some level of openness in order to engage with the Phonoautoboth activities.

Participants' interest around renewable energy and sustainability

Frequency of attendance at music events

A question about how often the attendees went to music events was introduced at the Belle & Sebastian Festival, given that the activities were taking place at a music festival, and was applied too at the Explorathon in Castlemilk and Beatroute Arts events. The majority of participants who responded to this question were frequent music event goers (festivals, concerts, gigs) either going very often (16%) or often (24%), which is unsurprising. Only 4% of participants “never” went to a music event, and 22% of participants, “rarely”.

Frequency of participants' attendance to music events

Part 4: Qualitative analysis of impact on participants

Based on the limited information from the postcards, there were some differences in the audience reached by the Phonoautoboth activities between events taking place in community settings, at the University of Glasgow (event at the Advanced Research Centre), and at the Belle & Sebastian Music Festival.

In terms of the demographic composition, while events held in community settings outside of the University had a strong family focus, with the largest groups being young children and parents, the event held at the university engaged a more adult audience. The music festival skewed heavily towards young adults (18-30) with a secondary older demographic (46-64) matching that it was a predominantly adult event.

Although overall the Phonoautoboth activities reached participants who generally hadn't had contact with University of Glasgow researchers before, events both at the University and other community events showed more level of previous contact and a more even distribution compared to the dedicated music festival where previous contact was rare. People who participated in events taking place at the University or in community settings had moderate interest in renewable energy, either actively engaging with the topic or being open to it. However, people who attended the event at the University of Glasgow's Advanced Research Centre showed a higher proportion of passive interest and a small proportion of disinterest. This might reflect the academic setting and a general openness to research, but perhaps with less active participation in research activities outside of formal studies. Above all, the music festival audiences had the highest level of interest and engagement with renewable energy. This could be because attendees of the festival who were already interested in this would then actively seek out the Phonoautoboth but does suggest strong potential for incorporating research activities or citizen science projects within music festivals.

A separate online survey was applied to a smaller subset of people (18 people, 14.4% of those that had direct conversations with volunteers and researchers) that attended the Belle & Sebastian festival. The results also suggest the engagement connected new audiences to the University of Glasgow. From the participants monitored using an online survey after the festival, half were adults aged between 31 - 45 years, 22% were adults between 18 - 30 years, and 22% between 46 - 64 years. Respondents were usually music events assistants, and all found the solar-powered mobile studio concept interesting. In this event, the Phonoautoboth activities reached participants who generally hadn't had contact with researchers from the University of Glasgow before – 83% had never been in contact with them before and 17%, rarely.

What impact did the programme have on the participants?

Based on the postcards and posterboards:

The Phonoautobothly aimed to showcase the use of renewable energy for power generation on a small scale. The event held at the Advanced Research Centre, University of Glasgow, was sustainably powered with two stages, one by hydrogen and one by solar energy. This was the largest public event ever held at the ARC, and was likely the first time participants had seen hydrogen powered generation storage and large scale batteries.

The information provided by participants in the postcards and on the posterboards indicated that the Phonoautobothly events influenced them positively, regarding their general attitude to environmental sustainability and renewable energy sources. They were surprised to find out about the environmental impact of music events and recording studios. and discussion around alternative energy sources prompted them to share their own personal commitments to sustainability. They also expressed interest in sharing their new knowledge on the topic with others.

More specifically, when asked about what a more sustainable future (including more sustainably powered music festivals) would look like to them, they focused on the positive emotions associated with solar powered music festivals as well as themes like practicality, reduced environmental impact, and a sense of hope for the future.

In conversation with the volunteer facilitators, respondents showed awareness of alternative sources of energy, such as solar and wind power, and through discussion, were inspired to consider potential applications of these and share new ideas. Common themes explored through the postcards revolved around harnessing solar energy for objects of daily use, transportation, and even counteracting the negative impacts of climate change. Similarly, wind energy also garnered interest, with ideas for wind-powered devices and infrastructure.

For some participants, the Phonoautobothly was their first time seeing an explicitly solar-powered event first hand, inciting curiosity and sparking questions to the researchers, such as, “How does it work when it’s dark outside/cloudy?”, “Where is the electricity stored?”, and “What if it rains?”. Some were also surprised about the size of the solar panels and thought many more would have been needed to run the Phonoautobothly, highlighting the perspective that exists around needing vast areas for solar panels in order to produce sufficient energy to power a machine.

Based on interview data with volunteer facilitator observations:

Observations from the volunteers facilitating the activities were also useful in gauging the impact the events had on participants from the public. A common theme was the fun and excitement generated through engaging with the music trailer and activities, noted both through observation as well as positive feedback shared directly by the participants. When asked to describe the eco-powered festival in one word on post-its,

respondents chose to write "Joy!", "Community", "Summer fun!", "Eco-powered", "Festival", and "Fun" (Attendees, WestFest 22 June).

The activities were enjoyable and successfully sparked longer conversations about music, clean energy, community energy, and engineering for many. The volunteers' general feeling was that the recording station was "brilliant" and "quirky", and highlighted its ability to provide a "fun" and "exciting" experience.

"The staff in the Phonoautoboth were spectacular. They made my son (who was 13 at the time) feel like a "real" musician, improved his confidence and have contributed to his continued interest in playing guitar and being in a band."

(Attendee, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

"My daughter [age 12] and her friend really enjoyed recording in the Phonoautoboth. The engineers, musicians, techs were very encouraging and great in getting them comfortable and engaged. We really enjoyed playing the tape back when we got home and me and my friend were pleased the kids had participated in a creative activity."

(Attendee, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

At events which were less busy and had fewer people approaching, which may typically be seen as less successful, the volunteers noted that the quieter environment enabled participants to stay longer, often being more deeply invested and spending significant time chatting with the Phonoautoboth researchers and decorating their cassette tapes. The volunteers observed that "interactions were more meaningful" and that "[participants] were really interested in the bothy and asked questions" (WestFest 22 June).

Based on the Belle & Sebastian Festival survey:

Based on a separate online survey applied to a subset of people, participants that engaged with the project at the Belle & Sebastian festival also reported that their experience with the Phonoautoboth was positive and engaging, providing a creative opportunity for making music as well as inspiration for learning more about

environmental sustainability. The information gathered from this survey indicated that the majority of participants were interested in getting involved in the environmental transition in Glasgow and suggested that the project promoted a positive attitudinal change towards it.

Almost all respondents enjoyed the Phonoautobothly interaction and activities, and three quarters agreed that the solar-powered music studio concept had made them curious to find out more about environmental sustainability. Although respondents' thoughts about the sustainability of music festivals and outdoor performances before attending the event varied, all thought renewable energy could benefit their community and around two thirds considered their interest and enthusiasm around it increased after engaging with the Phonoautobothly. Similarly, although thoughts about contributing somehow to Glasgow's transition to renewable energy after the event fluctuated, respondents shared they would prefer to attend musical festivals and outdoor performances that are sustainably powered in the future, and 75% considered that they had learned some practical actions they can take towards sustainability.

"It was so great to learn more about the mission behind the project. Learning more about how sustainability is such a big push in Glasgow was really great too. As a sustainability minor in school, I particularly enjoyed seeing the passion for it in another country. I also loved the feeling of going into the Phonoautobothly and seeing what the project was doing first hand and the impact of the project."

(Attendee, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

"I had not considered the footprint the recording industry has, but now can encourage friends who work in the industry to look into exploring more sustainable practices."

(Attendee, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

Additionally, the responses to this survey suggested that the Phonoautobothly promoted awareness of university research in the environmental transition in Glasgow, spanning both engineering and the music industry. Three quarters of respondents agreed that they are more aware of research around environmental transition to renewable energy in Glasgow after the event. Additionally, two thirds of respondents shared that they were interested in finding out more about this research at the University of Glasgow.

All festival goers that responded found the solar-powered mobile studio concept interesting and quoted that the sense of collaboration in the music trailer enhanced their enjoyment of the activity. "People were really impressed. The key moment: 'This is powered by solar energy - I can't believe this will happen like this.'" (Volunteer, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug).

The inclusive atmosphere brought about by the people involved (music enthusiasts and staff) was a key factor in fostering a sense of community and inspiration for some around this innovative project in Glasgow. "The atmosphere the organisers and the volunteers created was very friendly so everyone passing by actually stopped to take a look and discuss." (Volunteer, WestFest 22 June)

"I remember hanging out and talking with the staff while listening to the music people were making for a few hours - the staff were all really friendly and it was inspiring to hear all of the participants, regardless of skill level. My recording session was mainly a blur, but I felt honored to have Matt drumming on it!"
(Attendee, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

While only one performer who recorded in the studio responded to the survey, they indicated that the experience had given them new ideas about the connection between music festivals and sustainability, and the ability to record music outside studios.

"Nowadays I'm more inclined to rehearse with my band without the use of instruments that require electricity."

(Performer, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

Beatroute Arts Session - Based on observations and interview data from Beatroute staff, music tutors, and adults

The participants from the Beatroute Arts Centre charity highly enjoyed the Phonoautobothly activities, based on observations and interview data from staff, tutors, and participating adults. Having previously written a song inspired by a recent trip on the Forth and Clyde Canal, called 'The Boat Trip', the event provided a fantastic opportunity for the participants to record it. Beatroute music tutors and the Phonoautobothly arts researchers facilitated one-to-one recording sessions with the adults using the solar-powered production studio. For this specific event, having

musical instruments, microphones and recording gear at their disposal provided by the charity, and many of the group's participants being songwriters themselves who regularly record, made the activities even more engaging. At the end, everyone came together to make live music as a group, and companions and staff joined to listen to the song the participants had recorded. The pre-existing relationship between the project organisers and the charity laid the groundwork for a more meaningful partnership between the two.

“What [the Phonoautobothly] it's capable of doing and what it's capable of demonstrating is really inspiring. It is high academic research connecting to communities, and showing it is for everyone. Everyone can understand it is coming from music. (...) everyone loves music, and that commonality is what makes it interesting. You don't have to understand it to enjoy it.”

(Beatroute Director)

The trailer first arrived at the Beatroute Arts Centre in the summer time. Participants were intrigued by it, as it looked mysterious when it had not been opened. *“We saw it from the outside, I thought it was a hot dog truck [food truck]”* (Beatroute adult programme participant). It was a big surprise when they opened the trailer and used it for the first time. *“We have been using it for a couple of different things. For performing, like a portable stage, and recording.”* (Beatroute music tutor). During the interviews, it was mentioned by the participants and the staff that the Phonoautobothly allowed them to record in a relaxed atmosphere without noise and interruptions.

“If you are coming in here to record on your own, we hear a lot of noise from the rest of the building. But if we went out to record in the bothy, it would be different. It is useful for little recording projects and recordings with people with delicate and quieter voices. (...) It means you create a small and intimate space where you can record something really quiet without all the noise next door.”

(Beatroute music tutor)

Regarding the relation of the project with sustainability, the format sparked questions about other forms of energy, *“like wind farms”*, and made the participants think about music being powered by solar energy. The solar panels all over the trailer made them curious and made them think that *“everything is connected”*, as well as wondering how it functioned, *“I want to know how it works. If you use it at nighttime, does it work? Can you use it at night?”* (Beatroute adult programme participants).

What impact did the programme have on the volunteer facilitators?

The volunteers involved mostly included researchers from the University of Glasgow, with an interest in either the engineering or musical aspects of the Photoautobothly, and were supported to facilitate during the events. The experience of delivering the

Phonoautobothy activities and engaging with the public was enriching for them beyond the specific technical aspects of the project, as expressed through interviews with them after the events, and shared through survey data. "I feel that the key learning points for me were just around engaging the public and the logistical challenge that takes. My research plans to do this in some capacity so I feel from this perspective that I have learned." (Researcher volunteer).

They reported being impressed by the conversations they participated in around renewable energy and the use of solar power to run a music festival, indicating a greater understanding and more positive attitude around renewable sources of energy and their potential applications.

Overall, the Phonoautobothy helped to increase the volunteers' confidence with regards to public engagement, by providing them with insights into how to attract and engage the public, how to approach diverse audiences, and how to tailor communication to different levels of understanding. "Working in the Phonoautobothy gave me a clearer perspective on how to generate public engagement and impact. It was nice to see the Phonoautobothy activities acting as conversation starters and gradually bringing people's attention to environmental and sustainability issues." (Researcher volunteer).

On a scale of 1 to 10, their average confidence score with regards to carrying out public engagement with communities was recorded as higher by 1.8 after their volunteering experience, having initially been recorded as 6.9/10 before their involvement in the project. They also expressed that they greatly enjoyed the experience, even taking a more active role by engaging in jamming and playing instruments together themselves.

The Phonoautobothy experience allowed them to gain insights into public attitudes and varying levels of awareness regarding energy and climate change, as well as the logistical challenges and planning involved in successful public engagement activities. One volunteer stated, "I will definitely use what I have learned in this project in my future public engagement projects inside academia." (Volunteer researcher). Interestingly, the volunteers' involvement in this project also provided valuable learning opportunities for them beyond the specific technical aspects which running the activities entailed, showing how important teamwork can be and how easily team spirit

can be fostered through group activities. This was shared more specifically by one of the volunteers in an interview: "I'm surprised how such engaging activities can bring together and make a team of people that a few minutes ago didn't know each other." (Volunteer, referring to WestFest 22 June).

Another theme that came up around the volunteers' experience was the value of interdisciplinary collaboration, especially between the arts and humanities. Although collaboration between the fields was acknowledged as significant, the volunteers did not find that their involvement in the project provided a spark for generating new perspectives which could inform their future public engagement activities in this phase.

Given their different backgrounds, different volunteers gained different insights and learning from this project, and the mix of backgrounds was beneficial for learning from each other. While most were already involved in research, one volunteer who did not come from a research background shared that they learned a lot about research through their involvement with the Phonoautobothly and were positively surprised by the research being carried out on things that are normally taken for granted.

What impact did the programme have on the organisers?

The main organisers, Professor Matt Brennan, Dr Graeme Hunt, and Victor Camilo, all found participation in this project to be positive and enriching, both in terms of learning from each other and about each other's disciplines, as well as gaining experience with regards to public engagement and project management. Despite it being a learning curve, it was enjoyable, and Prof. Brennan stated, "I think we are now in a much

stronger, more experienced and knowledgeable position to design future public engagement projects."

Public engagement

Victor, a research assistant from the School of Culture and Creative Arts at the University of Glasgow, was employed to co-ordinate the programme, and reported in an interview that his involvement in the project broadened his experience in public engagement. The opportunity to interact with a diverse audience, including both adults and children, and to facilitate those interactions, was beneficial for him and helped in his professional growth. The project provided an environment for learning about public engagement and how to effectively engage with audiences of different demographics. Both Prof. Brennan and Dr Hunt, project co-leads, found that this was the case, despite having different backgrounds and previous levels of involvement with public engagement activities themselves.

The organisers also observed that, although initially attracting an audience was important, a key factor in engagement was also managing the transition between the entry point activities and the topic of music to the theme of renewable energy and environmental sustainability. Although the activities proved broadly successful in drawing people in and allowing these discussions to happen, other constraints such as limited time and many participants at once were found to be obstacles in this process.

Project management

Project management, and in particular managing an innovative project within a university framework, was another area in which the organisers gained valuable experience. Dr Hunt and Prof. Brennan acknowledged that it was an ambitious project

with many of the activities falling outside of their usual academic work. Although this was a challenge, described by Prof. Brennan as "a case of learning by doing", both for themselves as well as the university, it allowed them to gain a better understanding of how to carry out such work within a university framework, and what difficulties and opportunities to expect.

The co-leads of the project also pointed out that coordinating a large number of collaborators, who do not ordinarily interact with one another, was at times very stressful. Working well together proved to be a huge positive in dealing with this stress as Prof. Brennan and Dr Hunt shared it and found they were able to handle it together, highlighting the importance of good teamwork in handling difficulties within a project.

The project co-ordinator, Victor, quoted both project management as well as logistics in terms of practical experience gained in this project. Dealing with the set-up and operational aspects of the Phonoautobothy provided valuable lessons in the work that goes into executing such a project, beyond the research components.

Research and impact

Having realised the significance of factors beyond research in running a project, Victor also noted that his perspective on research and impact itself had changed. Working on this project helped him better understand how to think about and articulate the impact of his research, which was something he had previously found particularly challenging, specifically regarding his PhD applications. He plans to continue as a researcher with appreciation of his more mature approaches towards research.

Besides considering how the project influenced participants from the public, Prof. Brennan and Dr Hunt also learned about each other's disciplines (Professor of Popular Music and Research Associate in Systems, Power and Energy, respectively), and the nature of research in their respective fields. The Phonoautobothy provided circumstances for understanding how to integrate different types of research and consider how they can complement one another in this type of work.

What impact did the programme have on the wider music industry and Net Zero Glasgow & cross-sector partnerships?

The Phonoautobothy successfully fostered collaboration between academia, the arts, and community organisations, and proved capable of engaging diverse audiences.

According to external partners, the project highlighted the potential of music and cultural events to revitalise Glasgow city centre, as reported by researchers who acted as volunteer facilitators in the execution of the project. Vailla Cameron from Glasgow City Council noted that "it's really about how like culture and art can be used to to support kind of climate activity in local authorities." Katie Duffy, from Glasgow Life, backed this up, "...that thing about our city centre and the challenges facing our city

centre, and how music can help. animate, renew, make, make that a vibrant space again."

Through answers submitted in an online survey, applied only at the Belle & Sebastian festival, the only performer to respond expressed appreciation for the unexpected opportunity to record with their long-distance collaborator. This allowed them to produce something tangible from the experience, as well as inspiring new ideas regarding the option of recording outside of studios, and considering the link between sustainability and music festivals.

"I was visiting from overseas to play the concert, and it allowed me to unexpectedly record with my long distance collaborator".

(Performer, Belle & Sebastian 2&3 Aug)

The performer also showed a positive attitudinal change with regards to the environment as well as greater understanding of alternative sources of energy and their potential applications by stating that they would, in the future, prefer to perform at musical festivals and outdoor performances that are sustainably powered.

To round off this phase of the programme, a seminar was held on 18 February 2025, inviting key stakeholders to share their evaluation and learning, and to invite further discussion and reflection. This was a key opportunity to bring wider insights of longer-term outcomes. The data was collected and shared as an appendix to this report.

See page 46 Appendix: Dear Green Music Scene: Next Steps Seminar.

Event success highlights

The Phonoautobothy project succeeded in realising the intended aims, including fostering new engagement of the public with the University of Glasgow, influencing a greater understanding and positive attitudinal change in participants towards alternative sources of energy, and providing an opportunity for researchers to gain new skills in public engagement and form new partnerships.

The public participants found it to be exciting, and it worked well in engaging both adults and children. Through survey responses, there was confirmation that participation in the events was for many the first time coming into contact with the University of Glasgow, and learning about the research involved in implementing such a project. Volunteers facilitating the activities in both the mobile studio and the engineering stall found their involvement in the project helped connect them with one another, and increase their confidence in public engagement more generally. The organisers also found that they were able to learn about each other's disciplines through the project, and similarly reported development of their skills in public engagement.

Specifically with regards to the choice of activities hosted, the variety proved a positive factor in engaging various age groups and catering to different interests. For example, while younger people were drawn in by the engineering activity around wind-powered cars, parents were given the opportunity to get involved in the wider conversation with volunteers, and at times this stall was very busy. “It was an amazing conversation starter! It was a great hook and brought people into the engineering tent”. (Volunteer researcher).

The musical aspect and recording process also provided a useful link in conceptualising how music and sustainable energy sources can be connected. At the music festival setting in particular, this link generated interest around the sustainability aspect of the music industry from a participating musician. "Some people actually came to ask about the solar panels - it felt particularly about experimenting." (Volunteer researcher).

The choice of location for the Phonoautobothly at each of the events, in areas where a large audience would already be attending, and embedding the project within wider community events like festivals, was important in having people approach and engage, and proved a successful consideration as part of the project planning. Members of the public who may not necessarily be expecting to have conversations about energy and sustainability were drawn in by the musical aspect of the Phonoautobothly which acted as a hook, leading them to participate in the activities and spark discussions around environmental sustainability.

“I was impressed by how many people we were able to impact with this project. At first the idea sounded very wild, so it's not so much that I was skeptical, but I didn't know what to expect. It was a pleasure to work in this project and I would love to see the Bothy itself and the idea developing further.”

(Volunteer researcher).

Besides the intended outcomes, the Phonoautobothly provided a stage for golden moments. These were particular moments of social connection between participants, such as young siblings helping each other succeed in the engineering activities, and members of the Beatroute Arts charity sitting all together to listen to their recording of their song. For the performer who responded to the survey at the Belle & Sebastian

festival, the Phonoautobothly was an unexpected and positive surprise, allowing them to record with their long-distance collaborator.

Ideas for future development

The Phonoautobothly booth itself and wider activities provided an innovative, visually and aurally engaging, creative and fun format which inspired interest among new and diverse audiences. Participants were happy to share ideas and suggestions with regards to the future of the project and the ways in which they may be involved. Observations from organisers and facilitators were also noted with an eye towards making the most of the Phonoautobothly's potential.

Members of the audience were very keen for more opportunities to engage with the Phonoautobothly in different locations, with more activities, and to an even greater depth. A few participants mentioned that having more options for instruments to play, such as a keyboard, would enhance their experience. Some suggested incorporating more information about sustainability and the technical aspects of the studio - this could potentially be done through signage in or around the trailer, as well as through conversation with the volunteers. Other ideas for expanding the scope of the project were to use the trailer for other types of events, such as film festivals, which was suggested at the Belle & Sebastian festival, as well as organising a Phonoautobothly tour with resident artists.

With regards to the thematic content at the events, it was suggested that a greater connection between the recording studio and the engineering stall activities would be useful, complementing each other and making it clearer for audiences that they were part of the same programme. This could involve a shared focus on solar energy, further similar branding for the activities, a map or “treasure trail” type activity connecting the two, and/or other activities linking sustainability, engineering, and music. For example, at the events where Makey Makeys - which generate music through circuits - were used, this was very effective. The physical positioning of the activities in relation to each other was also a key factor in how connected participants perceived the activities to be and would be significant to consider in the future.

Finally, the organisers suggested that future plans could home in on further understanding the intended impact of the programme. The selected evaluation methods point towards a success in all aspects; however, the short project delivery window has meant the evaluation has been proportional. Having a better understanding on what evaluation methods might work, future programmes could build on this - for example, it would be useful to embed interviewing community partners over time to understand the impact it has had on attitudes.

Key learning for future events

The nature and innovative approach of this project, as acknowledged by the organisers, meant that much of the learning was accomplished through the 'doing'. Observations and key learning for better management and improvements in execution are detailed below.

Volunteers noted that the range of activities, despite being suitable for catering to a variety of participants, could be further tailored towards different audiences as well as demonstrating a clearer connection to each other. For example, in the first case the engineering activities were considered potentially too "young" for the music festivals where the audience was primarily adults only; however, at the more family-focused events, the engineering stall was in high demand. At times, this demand exceeded what the volunteers could host at any one time in the space, and events could benefit from a greater spread of similar activities to ease congestion and enhance capacity.

In terms of the role of the volunteers in delivering the activities, they shared that participants from the public were not always aware that they were researchers, despite them wearing University of Glasgow t-shirts. They suggested that having t-shirts or signage with more specific messaging ("I'm researching a more sustainable future, ask me questions!") might encourage more engagement from the public on sustainable energy or research in general. Having more specific roles and greater awareness of each other's backgrounds would also benefit the volunteers in being able to signpost to each other depending on specific topics participants may be interested in.

Due to the nature of volunteering, it was the case that some of the facilitators cancelled with very little notice. For future events, to avoid understaffing and ensure greater

capacity, it would be preferable to employ paid workers as the core delivery team - especially given the need for specific skills in people recruited to run the events, in particular someone trained to drive this unique vehicle. Volunteers would still be appreciated as additional capacity, enabling the events to run more smoothly and allowing more time for conversations rather than just running the activities.

Other logistical challenges revolved around events being confirmed relatively late, making it more difficult to recruit volunteers and plan collaboratively, such as assigning different roles to and tailoring the events for each audience more effectively. Future sessions will benefit from the learning of this phase to have things run more smoothly and be able to dedicate more time to public engagement planning.

Finally, in terms of practical issues, it was noted that the space could be developed to be more accessible, particularly for wheelchair users. Adapting the limited space or layout inside the Phonoautobothy with mobility considerations in mind and investing in a ramp at the entrance would be significant improvements.

Part 5: Quantitative Carbon Dioxide Equivalent Analysis

Carbon Dioxide Equivalent

When considering the sustainability aspects of the project there needs to be a metric by which comparisons may be made. This metric exists in the form of Carbon Dioxide Equivalent (CO₂e). While carbon dioxide (CO₂) is widely known for its effect on anthropogenic climate change, there are numerous other gases which also contribute to this phenomenon. However, not all these gases contribute to climate change to the same degree. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) of the United Nations has defined the so-called "Global Warming Potential" (or GWP) of these gases. This index is a measure of how much energy the emissions of 1 tonne of a gas will absorb over a given period of time, relative to the emissions of 1 tonne of carbon dioxide (CO₂). There are two aspects to this index, firstly that of the quantity of emissions produced and secondly a time component. The reason for this is that, for example, methane's effect on the climate is 28 times more severe than that of CO₂, but it does not stay in the atmosphere as long. Thus, the CO₂e value for any gas may be determined by multiplying the mass of any given gas by its GWP value. The GWP values for some common gases associated with global warming as given in the table below.

Gas	GWP
Carbon dioxide	1
Methane	28
Nitrous oxide	270
CFCs, HFCs, HCFCs	1000-10,000+

During the combustion process of fossil fuels in an internal combustion engine, both carbon dioxide and nitrous oxides (sometimes referred to as NO_x) are produced. In considering the CO₂e of any emissions, both the CO₂e of the emissions themselves and that of the transportation processes leading to the emissions must be considered. For example, during the use of a diesel generator the CO₂e of the gases produced during burning the fuel and that involved in the transportation of the fuel from "Well to Tank" (WTT) should be considered. In this analysis, life cycle analysis (LCA) which looks at embedded emissions for all processes during the production, use and disposal of items will not be considered.

An extensive list of CO₂e figures for fuel sources, refrigerants, etc has been compiled and is available on the UK government website:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/greenhouse-gas-reporting-conversion-factors-2024>.

Basic Carbon Dioxide Analysis

The data presented in the UK government website can be used to perform an estimation of the CO₂e emissions from a project, factory, item or business. This can be applied to the Dear Green Music Scene Festival at the ARC as part of WestFest, in which the

Phonoautobothy acted as one stage and another stage was build powered by a combination of battery and a hydrogen generator. This permits a comparison between the CO2e used by the renewable energy sources and a similarly calculated CO2e had the power been supplied by a diesel generator. The combined CO2e sum of the two stages results in a total value of the CO2e with which to perform the comparison.

The hydrogen stage

The telemetry from the battery system indicates how much power was used and when it was used. The combined hydrogen reactor and battery system operates in such a way as that when the charge remaining in the battery drops below a prescribed level, the hydrogen reactor kicks in and recharges the battery. In the case of the power supply to the Hydrogen stage, this was not actually required due to the very low energy requirement of the stage compared to the storage capacity of the battery. The reactor was only briefly switched on for demonstration purposes and so the CO2e for the hydrogen reactor is not included in this analysis as it did not contribute to the power supply for the stage in any meaningful way.

Detailed analysis of the graph shows that over the course of the festival 1.389 kWh of power were used in total. For simplicity the calculations presented herein will assume that this can be approximated to 5 hours at 220W and 1 hour at 270W. This difference was due to the first 5 hours being support bands and the final hour being the headline act.

This is $(5\text{hrs} \times 0.22\text{kW}) + (1\text{hr} \times 0.27\text{kW}) = 1.37\text{ kWh}$

This gives a total of 1.37 kWh used which is an error of only 1.4% and as such is a very reasonable approximation to use.

Figure showing the telemetry from the battery system with time shown on the x axis and power on the y axis.

The Solar Stage

Unlike the Hydrogen stage, the Solar Stage did not have a headline act, so all six hours were at a similar level of energy consumption to one another. There was no telemetry for this stage, so repeated monitoring of energy consumption was instituted leading to a fairly consistent average power draw of 180W. This means that for the Solar Stage a total energy usage of 1.08kWh was used.

Emissions

In order to determine the emissions, the Solar Stage obtained its energy from the sun and there are similarly no emissions due to electricity transmission so the emissions in terms of CO₂e would be zero. For the Hydrogen Stage, since batteries were the primary source of power and these need to be charged *a priori*, it is necessary to consider the associated emissions with the charging process. While it is possible that the batteries themselves may have been charged solely using renewable sources, for the sake of this comparison it will be assumed that they were charged using the national grid. It is not immediately obvious; however, two figures are required to calculate the CO₂e value for the electricity used to charge the batteries. This first, as might be expected is the CO₂e for the electricity itself. This figure is found in the “UK Electricity” tab from the UK government figures spreadsheet mentioned previously. In addition to this it is important to consider also the CO₂e involved in the transmission of that electricity from power source to the customer. This is found in the “Transmission and distribution” tab of the same document. So, the final value for the CO₂e per unit of electricity is found by summing the contribution from the electricity emission factor and the transmission and distribution:

	CO ₂ e per kWh
Emission Factor	0.20705
Transmission and distribution	0.01830
Total	0.22535

Considering that for the Hydrogen Stage a total of 1.37kWh was used, this constitutes:

$$1.37 \times 0.22535 = 0.309 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}$$

Thus, for the combined Solar stage and Hydrogen Stage a total of 0.309 kg CO₂e constituted the total emissions for the festival.

Diesel Generators

A more traditional method of power generation at festivals is the use of diesel generators. To determine the size of generator required, it is first necessary to calculate the power requirements. Once the total power required by the various components of the stage setup are known then this total power draw will determine the size of the generator required. Looking at the equipment for the Hydrogen Stage:

PA Item	Power rating
2x RCF J8 - PA https://www.rcf.it/en/products/product-detail/evox-j8	2x1400W=2800W
2x db Technologies FMX10 - Monitors https://www.dbtechnologies.com/en/products/flexsys/fmx10/	2x800W=1600W
1x Allen & Heath SQ5 Desk https://www.allen-heath.com/hardware/sq/sq-5/	75W
Total for Hydrogen Stage	4475W

For the Solar stage, the requirements were less so only half the PA was used there, plus a separate sounds desk making the power requirements 1400+800+75=2275W. This makes the total power requirement for the PA and mixing desks for both stages require a combined total of:

$$4475W + 2275W = 6750W = 6.75kW$$

To be able to supply this power a 10kVA generator with a power factor of 0.8 would be required. The power factor of a diesel generation is the ratio of the real power that is usable to the apparent power. A power factor of 0.8 is common for diesel generators. So, this would be capable of delivering up to 8kW of power, which is sufficient for the maximum power draw of the equipment calculated at 6.75 kW.

For the purposes of calculating the CO₂e value for the use of the diesel generators it is again necessary to consider two figures from the UK government website. This time, the first figure to use is found on the “Fuels” tab and it accounts for the CO₂e for burning the fuel to produce the electricity. This value is listed for the diesel emission factor is 0.25403 kg CO₂e per kWh generated. Next it is necessary to consider the “Well to Tank” emissions, these are given on the WTT-fuels tab and the value for diesel is 0.06181kg CO₂e per kWh. This gives a total of:

$$0.25403 + 0.06181 = 0.31584 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e per kwh}$$

Now the total CO₂e for the two stages may be calculated for the scenario in which diesel generators had been used to provide the necessary power.

Stage	Energy used (kWh)	kg CO ₂ e
Hydrogen	1.37	1.37 x 0.31584=0.4327008
Solar	1.08	1.08 x 0.31584 = 0.3411072
Total	2.45	0.773808

It should also be noted that there would also be emissions associated with the transport of the Phonoautobothly, Battery and Hydrogen reactor. However, the alternative method of powering the festival would entail the use of diesel generators and for the sake of this comparison, it is assumed that the transport of the diesel generators and fuel tank would have a comparable emission to that of the transport of the renewable power sources and so they would cancel each other out.

Thus, the diesel generator would have produced a total of 0.774 kg CO_{2e}. Since the calculated CO_{2e} for the renewable power sources was 0.309 kg CO_{2e}. This means a saving of 0.465 kg CO_{2e} was made. This represents a saving of 60% in terms of carbon emissions!

Considering generator efficiency

The above calculations for the diesel generator assume that the generator was operating at its maximum efficiency. However, generator efficiency decreases with lower load as a percentage of its maximum load capacity. This means that had a 10kVA diesel generator been used, it would in fact have been operating at a significantly lower efficiency. It is possible to take this into account by means of calculating the efficiency curve for the generator. The US Department of Energy (DOE) National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) created a Hybrid Optimization Model for Electric Renewables (HOMER). HOMER allows for calculations for the optimisation of integration of both renewables and diesel generators in small grids, for example in remote villages. As such it has the capacity to calculate the efficiency of the renewable and fossil fuel components. Using the calculation method detailed in HOMER, the efficiency Curve can be generated using:

$$\eta_{gen} = \frac{3600 \times P_g}{\rho_f (F_o + F_1 P_g) LHV_f}$$

Where the symbols used are defined in the table below and the 3600 is the number of seconds in an hour which is used to convert values given on a per second basis to values per hour.

Symbol	Meaning
η_{gen}	Generator efficiency value
P_g	Power load
ρ_f	Fuel Density
LHV_f	Lower Heating Value of the fuel
F_o	Fuel curve intercept coefficient
F_1	Fuel curve slope

Generating the efficiency curve

In order to accomplish this, certain details about the generator need to be known. Thus, for the purposes of this calculation an example of a typical generator that might be used for these purposes has been chosen. This is the Pramac GSW10P 10kVA / 8kW 3-Phase Perkins Engine Diesel Generator. For this generator the following specifications for fuel consumption in litres per hour (l/hr) can be found relating to the Prime Rated Power (PRP), in this case 8KW:

Fuel consumption @ 75% PRP 1.99 l/hr
 Fuel consumption @ 100% PRP 2.58 l/hr

This allows for the calculation of F_o and F_1 as follows. Starting with F_1 which is the slope of the curve:

$$F_1 = \frac{2.58 - 1.99}{8 - 6} = 0.295$$

Once the slope is known the intercept can then be determined:

$$\text{Intercept} = 1.99 - (6 \times 0.295) = 0.22 \text{ l/hr}$$

Since the required value, F_o is not the intercept itself, but the intercept coefficient, it is necessary to divide the intercept by the rated capacity of the generator, 8kW to give:

$$F_1 = \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{rated capacity}} = \frac{0.22 \text{ l/hr}}{8 \text{ kW}} = 0.0275 \frac{\text{l}}{\text{hr} \cdot \text{kW}}$$

Using the values of 43.2 MJ/kg for the LHV of Diesel and 820kg/m³ for the density of diesel it is now possible to calculate the efficiency for any given power load by substituting these values into the equation for the efficiency curve.

$$\eta_{gen} = \frac{3600 \times P_g}{\rho_f (F_o + F_1 P_g) LHV_f} = \frac{3600 \times P_g}{820 (0.0275 \times 0.295 P_g) \cdot 43.2}$$

The resulting efficiency curve showing the efficiency of the generator vs the percentage of the maximum output is shown below.

Efficiency Curve

The efficiency curve shows the efficiency with respect to the chemical energy input to the generator versus the electrical energy output. It is common to take the maximum efficiency of the generator and use this as a measure against which to judge the

performance. It is perhaps misleading, but this is sometimes the figure referred to as the “efficiency” of the generator. A more transparent term in use for this metric is the “capacity”, though this has the issue that it might be confused with the kVA value for the generator. This metric is useful as a measure of how well the generator is performing under a given load versus how well it performs at its maximum. Converting the above efficiency curve to show this yields the following normalised efficiency curve:

As can be seen from the normalised efficiency curve, when the output is over 75% there is minimal drop in the efficiency of the generator. Even for 50% load, the generator is still functioning at over 90% of its maximum efficiency. For under 25% however the drop off is very steep. While the efficiency at 25% load is still 80% and thus might seem to be reasonable, consider a case where over time an energy supply of 80kWh was required. At 25% load and this would use 32.4 litres of diesel, whereas to generate this at 100% load would use only 25.8 litres of diesel. This is an increase in fuel consumption of 25%. Clearly as the load decreases further below the 25% mark, this increase in fuel consumption per kWh only gets worse. But is such a low load realistic in actual real-world cases? A two-year study in 2014-15 by Watt-Now in Holland showed that 77% of generators have an average load of less than 20% of their maximum load and that the peak load was less than 50% of the capacity for 69% of generators. This indicates that this presents a significant issue in the use of diesel generators at live events. Not only is it significant in terms of emissions, but also in wasted fuel.

In terms of determining the fuel consumption, this may be calculated now that the efficiency of the generator is known. This is the volume flow rate, \dot{V} in l/hr.

$$\dot{V} = \frac{3600 \times P_g}{\eta_{gen} \cdot \rho_f \cdot LHV_f} = \frac{3600 \times P_g}{\eta_{gen} \times 43.2 \times 820}$$

Thus, for any given load, determine the efficiency of the generator and substitute in the load, P_g and the calculated efficiency, η_{gen} to yield the volume flow rate. Armed with the amount of fuel consumed it is then possible to determine the CO₂e for the given load. To determine the CO₂e value for the combined Hydrogen and Solar stages had they been powered by the diesel generator chosen the first step is to examine how big the load was and for how long. This is information already at hand and is summarised in the following table.

Stage	Load	Number of hours
Hydrogen	0.22kW	5
Hydrogen	0.27kW	1
Solar	0.18kW	6

This means that 0.4kW was the total load for 5 hours and 0.45kW was the total load for the last hour. Using this then the efficiency and volume flow rates can be calculated by applying the respective formulae to give the following.

Duration	Load (kW)	Efficiency (%)	Volume flow rate (l/hr)	Fuel Used (l)
5 hours	0.4	12.0267	0.338	1.69
1 Hour	0.45	12.9643	0.353	0.353
Total Fuel used				2.043

As in the previous CO₂e calculations, it is necessary to consider the CO₂e for both the fuel itself and that associated with the travel from well to tank. Using the same tabs in the document but this time per litre of fuel gives:

$$Total\ CO_2e = WTT + Fuel\ CO_2e = 0.61101 + 2.51279 = 3.1238\ kg\ CO_2e\ per\ litre$$

So, for 2.043 litres of diesel fuel used the emissions were 6.381kg CO₂e.

When compared to the previous calculation which gave an emissions total of 0.774 kg CO₂e, it is clear that the value when efficiency is taken into account is almost 10 times greater. This is why it so important to consider the load placed upon generators when determining the emissions. Based upon this calculation, by using the renewable power generation sources the festival saved 6.072 kg CO₂e. This represents a saving of 95%.

Future plans

Overall, this phase of the programme has demonstrated that the Phonoautobothly is a creative way of engaging communities in Glasgow with sustainable energy through music and engineering. By being part of a series of events, it has engaged audiences who have not engaged with the University of Glasgow before, as well as those who are actively interested in sustainability and those who don't go out of their way to engage otherwise. It has been a valuable process for the volunteers and organisers, and an opportunity to gain much more confidence and understanding around engaging public audiences, as well as learning and managing the operational elements of maintaining and coordinating such a unique trailer.

As per the project plan, the Phonoautobothly trailer has been donated to Beatroute Arts as the charity partner. The project will continue to be developed for further engagement with communities, and Beatroute Arts are currently looking to scope and assess the viability of the trailer for future hires and events.

Find out more on [their website www.beatroutearts.com/phonoautobothly](http://www.beatroutearts.com/phonoautobothly)

Budget Analysis

Direct Project Costs	Description	Budgeted Costs (£)	Actual Costs (£)	Notes
Staff Resources	Research Assistant	£10,231.56	£10,231.56	
	Surveying, Analysis, and support during project	£5,040.00	£5,040.00	
	Support and materials- final seminar	0.00	£405.55	Final Seminar not originally planned, but deemed important
	Idlefield artist fees	£12,000.00	£12,000.00	
Other Costs	Doors Open Day	£900.00	£0	DOD events did not happen due to restrictions
	9th June Westfest	£1,000.00	£0	No costs associated with hire/staffing/towing
	15th June Westfest	£4,000.00	£1,034.07	Payment of artists covered by MusArc. Renewable power heavily discounted
	22nd June Westfest	£1,000.00	£0	No costs associated with hire/staffing/towing
	Beatroute Arts	£1,000.00	£501.67	Materials already purchased
	B&S	£2,000.00	£1,744.07	
	Doors Open Day times 2	£2,000.00	£0	DOD events did not happen due to restrictions
	Explorathon	£1,000.00	£467.50	Materials already purchased and on weekday so no towing costs
	Workshop space	0.00	£1,000.00	Extra costs incurred in the creation of the Phonoautobothy
	Maintenance	0.00	£1921.00	Funds not applied to DOD events used for winter prep and maintenance
	Tool Hire	0.00	£600.00	Additional costs for tools required for construction of Phonoautobothy
Total		£40,171.56	£34,945.42	
Remaining			£5226.14	Potential to be used for second "Dear Green Music Scene" festival pending no-cost extension approval. See Legacies section.

The analysis of the budget yield two main observations, the first was the Doors Open Days events did not occur due to certain restrictions. These restrictions were the requirement to move the Phonoautobothy on a weekday before 5pm imposed by the University Logistics department for towing of the trailer. This meant that the Phonoautobothy would need to be stored on site at the location of the Doors Open Days event Friday-Monday for the weekend events. There proved to be no suitable locations willing to do so and as such neither Doors Open Days events were able to proceed. This left £2900 unspent. The other observation was the additional cost associated with the construction of the Phonoautobothy. These totalled £1600 that was not budgeted for. However, the costs for the WestFest events on the 9th and 22nd of June were significantly lower than anticipated. This was in large part due to the towing of the trailer being undertaken by Idlefield and so at no cost to the project. As such the budgeted costs associated with these two Westfest events coupled with the savings on the "Dear Green Music Scene" festival was applied to the additional manufacturing and maintenance costs, which were easily covered by this.

Legacies

The legacy actions of the Phonoautobothly can be split into two parts: (1) the physical mobile unit itself; and (2) the continuation of the Dear Green Music Scene festival in 2025 and beyond.

Examining the physical aspect first, the Phonoautobothly was constructed using upcycled materials as far as possible to further focus on the sustainability values which are at the heart of the project. As a vehicle which by necessity travels upon public roads, it is subject to annual maintenance checks both electrical and mechanical. During the course of the most recent of these checks, mechanical failures were noted, the repair of which would cost significantly more than the value of the vehicle. This was primarily due to the age and source of the parts no longer being available and requiring bespoke replacement parts to be manufactured to conduct necessary repairs. As such, the Phonoautobothly as a mobile unit has had to be retired. The Phonoautobothly was donated to Beatroute Arts as part of the project plan, and they have purchased a retired Glasgow subway carriage and installed it within their grounds. At time of writing, the current plan is to extract the solar PV and music equipment from the chassis of the Phonoautobothly and install them in this Subway carriage. This permits the Phonoautobothly to continue in its mission as a community space demonstrating the use of renewable energy in the live music sector in perpetuity.

The Dear Green Music Scene festival 2025 built on the success of our 2024 event, adding some extra attractions and activities for the public to engage with. In addition to music, the festival offered numerous activities designed to stimulate conversation and creativity around sustainability and renewable energy generation. A drop-in stop-motion animation workshop was popular utilising sustainable materials to make short films. The public was invited to explore the ARC Maker Space, and there was also the option to watch the thought-provoking documentary “Cuba’s Life Task: Combatting Climate Change” directed by Daniesky Acosta with Helen Yaffe from the University of Glasgow. The Carbon Screen Test invited attendees to check the climate impact of their favourite films and TV shows, encouraging reflection on sustainability in everyday life. In total, the had a footfall of some 978 people, highlighting strong public interest in sustainable and creative community events.

Of the remaining project funding (£5226.14) a total of £4480 was allocated to the Dear Green Music Scene 2025 event. Once again, due to the overwhelming success of the event, Hannah Campbell (Events and Exhibitions Producer) at the ARC is already scoping possibilities for the event to be run again in 2026 next year pending securing additional funding.

Conclusion

The Phonoautoboth project reached new audiences and was successful in raising awareness about climate change and renewable energy, particularly among those who may not typically engage with these topics.

This solar-powered multi-purpose music trailer prototype provided audiences in Glasgow with a tangible demonstration of renewable energy in action, which helped people to see how solar power can be used to power real-world applications, putting theory into practice.

Situating the Phonoautoboth in non-scientific spaces, such as music festivals and concerts, allowed people who were not expecting to engage with science to get involved with the activities.

Engaging people with the topic in a fun and accessible way promoted a change in their behaviour, with some participants expressing they were more likely to consider using renewable energy sources or reduce their carbon footprint after engaging with the project.

The emissions analysis showed that the use of renewable energy in powering the “Dear Green Music Scene Festival” yielded significant savings in terms of the carbon dioxide equivalent versus use of diesel generators. Furthermore, it showed the importance of considering the generator efficiency when making such calculations.

Appendix - Dear Green Music Scene:

Next Steps Seminar (February 2025)

The following information is based on presentations and discussions from the Seminar, which was held at the ARC on 18 February 2025. Many of the ideas that came out and conclusions that were drawn from the project, presented in previous chapters, were highlighted at the seminar, confirming the success of the project and its future potential.

Following the first completed phase of the project, there was consideration for how the Phonoautobothly could work outside the University. This would involve mapping its full cost including maintenance, insurance, staffing, and sustainability, and deciding on a business model. The goal would be to create a sustainable, accessible model that can be replicated for more impact and adapted to different contexts, including for rural communities with limited access to recording studios and gigs.

In the future, the multipurpose trailer could be further developed to make it more functional, robust, and versatile, allowing it to be used in a wider range of contexts. This could involve making it more mobile, by making it an autonomous vehicle and removing the need for it to be towed, in order to be more easily deployed at festivals and events. A further focus point could involve enhancing features that worked to make them more intentional as part of the trailer's design, such as a recording studio or a stage for musicians. For this, expanding collaborations and applying for long-term funding opportunities is being considered.

The project could also be used to engage more communities, particularly those that are most impacted by climate change. This could involve taking the Phonoautobothly to rural communities (a benefit of its portability) or collaborating with community groups to develop new ways of using the multipurpose trailer. There is enormous potential for inspiring and including communities in high deprivation areas, pushing for further consideration of how to include communities more in conversations about the future business model of the project.

“There is a human link between the Phonoautobothly concept and the community. It is important to align the aims of the charity that will take care of the bothy with the project goals. It is about the human story and how music connects us. People that have the least voice and the least impact. If we are on a mission for the Phonoautobothly, the human part is essential.”

(Beatroute Arts Director).

The multipurpose trailer was praised by public engagement specialists and professionals from the screen sector and events industry for its versatility, ability to reduce noise and carbon emissions, and potential to enhance accessibility for people with hearing impairments. Next steps may involve using the project in the future to collaborate with other sectors, such as the screen industry, to promote sustainable practices.